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Kundalini Yoga on Self-Objectification among Selected Female Pageant Contenders in Mariveles, Bataan

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of Kundalini Yoga on female pageant contenders' self-objectification. Kundalini Yoga is a spiritual and physical practice that combines dynamic movement, breathing techniques, meditation, and chanting to awaken inactive energy believed to be at the base of the spine and channel it upward through the body's energy centers to attain spiritual enlightenment and self-awareness. 15 female pageant contenders aged 17 to 24 from Mariveles, Bataan, actively engaged in the study. Researchers assigned participants to four (4) Kundalini Yoga sessions or a control group, which received a one-time mindfulness webinar. At the post-test, the study observed that women who engaged in yoga sessions exhibited lower self-objectification ($p = 0.018$, $z = -2.366$), with a high effect size of 0.89. This study highlights that Kundalini yoga helps reduce self-objectification in female pageant participants, boosting their self-esteem. To improve future research, it is important to include a wider range of participants and age groups for more dependable results on self-objectification interventions. Furthermore, examining various yoga styles and teaching methods is vital for understanding their effects on women's body image. Additionally, considering venue factors such as atmosphere, facilities, and timing is crucial, as they greatly impact the success of interventions.

Keywords: *female, self-objectification, Kundalini Yoga, pageant contenders, mindfulness exercise*

Introduction

Self-objectification is a phenomenon that occurs when women view themselves as sexual objects, with their physical attractiveness being the sole criterion for others to derive pleasure and pass judgment on them (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997 as cited by Saunders, 2024; Ward et al., 2023). It is a psychological process where an individual initially perceives themselves as a physical object and only secondarily as a human being (Poon et al., 2023). Meanwhile, the Department of Health outlined that anorexia nervosa is a serious eating disorder characterized by restricted food intake followed by compensatory behaviors, such as vomiting, excessive exercise, or fasting to prevent weight gain, which is more prevalent among women, especially teenagers (0.3%), and can be attributed to social and environmental factors (Mohajan & Mohajan, 2023; Tannous et al., 2022). Body image anxiety, linked to self-objectification, often leads women to prioritize appearance over body functionality, contributing significantly to disorders (Murray et al., 2024). As stated by the World Health Organization (2021), failing to address this issue may affect physical and mental health, making it a crucial but often disregarded concern among current societal challenges.

Furthermore, there are also positive outcomes associated with self-objectification, although this correlation holds true only when self-objectification remains minimal. Engaging in regular self-assessment can unveil individual accomplishments, contribute to overall health, and reinforce self-esteem. Research suggests that asserting control over one's life can mitigate the stress induced by feelings of surveillance and internalization. Additionally, this sense of control can foster a profound sense of well-being and instill the belief that individuals have the capacity to improve themselves and cultivate confidence, even in instances where they may deviate from societal norms (Fioravanti et al., 2022; Stevens & Griffiths, 2020).

Fredrickson and Roberts (1997) state that self-objectification serves as a survival mechanism for women, offering several advantages. Notably, when women are perceived as attractive in society, they tend to experience greater social mobility and recognition, have increased dating opportunities, and encounter reduced instances of work discrimination. This aligns with research indicating that physical attractiveness has a stronger correlation with social outcomes for women than for men (Mirucka & Kisielewska, 2022; Alaei et al., 2022; Dwivedi, 2021). However, Objectification theory suggests that women who self-objectify are predisposed to negative subjective feelings, potentially leading to psychological disorders such as eating disorders, and consequent devaluation of self-worth following societal beauty standards (Ward et al., 2023; Poon et al., 2023; Prnjak et al., 2021; De Wilde et al., 2020)

Several researchers denote that there is a need for individual-based strategies to prevent women from engaging in self-objectification, emphasizing programs that will help adolescents to focus on their inner capabilities rather than their external appearance (Winner-Bachus, 2022; Cox & Tylka 2022; Dwivedi, 2021). Previous research explored the relationship between physical activity and body image (Putra et al., 2020). Additionally, there have been studies that indicate that mindfulness-based physical activity such as yoga may play a significant role in mitigating one of the self-objectification's disturbing impacts, which is the eating disorder (Diers et al., 2022; Dignard, 2022)

According to Brandão et al. (2024), Kundalini yoga directs attention to internal states, fostering heightened awareness that potentially diminishes the focus on outward appearance, thereby contributing to a healthier relationship with one's body. These support research that engagement in sports and physical activity, including yoga, may protect women and girls from self-objectification, other

researchers detailed that mindfulness-based activity is associated with various psychological advantages, such as improved mood, increased self-esteem, and body satisfaction across different age groups (Valdez, 2023; Balciuniene et al., 2022; McMahon et al., 2021). Moreover, the study by Winner-Bachus (2022) indicates that mindfulness-focused interventions can improve women's body experiences and reduce self-objectification by fostering awareness and the ability to respond to individual needs.

Regardless of yoga's potential benefits for well-being, there is still a need to assess its effectiveness as an intervention, especially for beauty pageant contestants (Maxwell & Katyal, 2022; Neumark-Sztainer et al., 2020). In line with this, Carpenter and Churchill's (2023) study found that participants, particularly adolescent females who compete in pageants, tend to lose weight. Beauty contests, which set certain beauty standards, remain to be one of the detrimental factors that lead women to objectify (Srivastava, 2020; Rohmatin & Habsari, 2020; Powers, 2021). Prior research suggests that women in their adolescence should be the primary focus of contemporary study, considering them prone to self-objectification (Daniels et al., 2020; Sandhu & Sandhu, 2021). Furthermore, the lack of research in the Philippines on Kundalini yoga's impact on self-objectification in women highlights the need for additional research to address potential mental and cognitive implications for Filipina women (Kalimi, 2023; Dayrit & Alibudbud, 2022; Cortez & Alfonso, 2020).

Research Questions

This research aims to investigate how to empower women experiencing self-objectification, offering practitioners and organizations insights into the role of mindfulness-based exercises in addressing such issues. Furthermore, it provides a valuable foundation for future researchers exploring related studies. The researchers selected female participants aged 17 to 24 from Mariveles, Bataan, who had previously competed in any type of beauty pageant. The following hypotheses will be looked at and addressed in this study:

1. Is there a significant difference in pre-and post- test scores of self-objectification in the experimental group?
2. Is there a significant difference in pre-and post- test scores of self-objectification in the control group?
3. Is there a significant difference between the experimental and control groups in the post- test scores of self-objectification?

Literature Review

The Concept of Self-Objectification

According to Fredrickson and Roberts (1997), who introduced the theory of objectification, it can be defined as women evaluating themselves from a third- person perspective. Winn and Cornelius (2020) emphasized that adopting a third-person perspective is key to identifying self-objectification but insufficient for its categorization, arguing it also involves a focus on appearance. Elizabeth Daniels et al. (2020) noted that media portrayals, societal standards, social media, peer pressure, and internalized gender stereotypes exacerbate this issue, highlighting the need for cultural shifts and interventions to promote a healthier understanding of body image and self-worth for women and girls.

While self-objectification can have both positive and negative outcomes, it is crucial to consider its broader impacts. On the positive side, Winn & Cornelius (2020) suggest that women who self-objectify often modify their physical features to meet societal and cultural standards, engaging in routines like makeup application, hairstyling, and following fashion trends. These practices can be empowering, potentially enhancing social and economic opportunities.

However, self-objectification also has significant negative effects on women's mental health and overall well-being. Researches found that environmental factors promoting appearance enhancement, such as plastic surgeries and edited images, contribute to body dissatisfaction, impaired cognitive functioning, low self-esteem, and more severe issues like eating disorders, depression, and even suicide (Wang et al., 2021; Chen et al., (2021); Hu et al., 2024; Geng et al., 2020; Guo et al., 2021; Wang & Li, 2020)).

Justifiably, the recent investigation focuses primarily on addressing this issue in a Western context. Gattino et al. (2023) found that among 2,165 adolescents in European countries, body shame and body surveillance, both major factors in self-objectification, are considered to be higher in women than men in the UK, Poland, and Romania, while only body surveillance is significant in Iranian samples. Similarly, they suggest exploring this topic in non- Western countries to identify its potential risks and protective factors. On the other hand, King and Iwamoto (2022) reported that among 554 Asian American women, 37.2% fall into a high self-objectification class, exhibiting higher rates of eating disorders and depression, while 40.1% fall into a moderate class. Hence, further research on this subject that includes various regions of the world can greatly enhance the current body of literature.

The Role of Pageantry in Self-Objectification

The Philippines is widely acknowledged as the homeland of pageantry, encompassing events from the simplest local barangay beauty contests to the most esteemed national competitions. Beauty pageants have long been intertwined with the nation's cultural identity (Guillen, 2023). However, there is ongoing debate about whether pageants empower women or contribute to their objectification. Advocates argue that pageantry offers a platform for women to demonstrate their intelligence, talent, and advocacy, fostering personal growth and enjoyment (Salazar & Moneva, 2020). Conversely, critics contend that pageants increase women's vulnerability to self-objectification (Rohmatin & Habsari, 2020; Srivastava, 2020; Sy et al., 2021).

Pageantry often promotes the idealization and objectification of the female body by judging contestants on their physical appearance

and presentation (Powers, 2021). This supports other researchers stating that women who join beauty contests are objectified. This is evident through the use of sponsorships, product promotions, and advertising

that utilize women in an instrumental manner. Furthermore, the emphasis on ideal body types, makeup, high heels, and glamorous gowns—elements central to pageantry—also contributes to self-objectification (Guillen, 2023; Rohmatin & Habsari, 2020). Similarly, He (2022) emphasizes that such unrealistic body standards, perpetuated through various media, contribute to eating disorders like anorexia nervosa. This leads to body dissatisfaction and an intense desire to achieve a romanticized thinness among pageant contenders.

The Influence of Mindfulness Exercise on Women's Body Image

Rodgers et al. (2023) note that concerns about body image, including weight and other aspects of appearance, are now widespread worldwide, often in older women. On the other hand, Jessica Alleva et al. (2020) describe positive body image as a multifaceted construct that broadly captures an "overarching love and respect for the body." This concept encompasses not only acceptance and appreciation of one's body but also behaviors and attitudes that promote body satisfaction and self-care—in efforts to encourage mindfulness, Valdez (2023) stated that mindfulness can reduce anxiety-inducing thoughts, such as body surveillance, by increasing awareness. Being present in our bodies helps us recognize internal cues like hunger and satiation, promoting healthy eating habits. Focusing on how we feel rather than look allows us to appreciate our body's function and reduces susceptibility to objectification and other similar issues.

In line with this, a mindfulness activity such as yoga significantly influences body image by fostering body awareness and responsiveness. Practitioners are encouraged to listen to and appreciate their body's functions and sensations rather than trying to change their body or push its physical limits (Cox & Tylka, 2020; Piran & Neumark-Sztainer, 2020). This mindful approach helps reduce self-objectification and promotes a positive body image. In addition, Diers (2022) has shown that regular yoga practice can improve self-esteem, reduce body dissatisfaction, and enhance overall mental and physical well-being.

However, even if yoga is proven to be an ancient practice with various forms that offer significant mental and physical health benefits. Different approaches cater to diverse needs and impacts. According to Valdez (2023), Hatha yoga, a commonly used style, improves body appreciation and foster an enhanced self-esteem. Given these advantages, further research should explore how other forms of yoga, such as Kundalini and Vinyasa, impact self-objectification and overall well-being. Additionally, understanding the long-term effects of consistent yoga practice and its potential integration into holistic health programs could provide deeper insights into its role in promoting mental and body image wellness (Winner-Bachus, 2022).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs an experimental approach wherein the researcher manipulates conditions, specifically Kundalini Yoga, to investigate its impact on the participants (Kazdin, 2021). The study randomly assigns participants to either an experimental group (e.g., Kundalini yoga program) or a control group without the intervention, ensuring that any observed differences are likely due to the intervention rather than pre-existing participant characteristics. Additionally, a within-subject design with a pretest/posttest approach is used in this study, measuring participants twice, before and after a single treatment, to account for different levels of independent variables (Montoya, 2022). The study primarily focuses on quantitative data, with participants providing detailed explanations to clarify the data for further analysis.

Participants

The study focuses on female pageant participants between 17 to 24 years old in Mariveles, Bataan. In addition, inclusion is based on an average score on Lindner and Tantleff-Dunn's Self-Objectification Beliefs and Behaviors Scale (SOBBS) (Lindner & Tantleff-Dunn, 2017). The primary objective is to examine the impact of Kundalini yoga on self-objectification of female pageant contenders. However, individuals who are currently pregnant or have given birth in the last year are ineligible due to potential health concerns related to Kundalini yoga, as well as those with prior experience in the said intervention are excluded from participation (Alleva et al., 2020). Participants in the experimental group who attended only one or two sessions were not included in the study. The exclusion was enforced to guarantee that any changes in self-objectification observed are specifically attributed to Kundalini yoga.

Instrument

The researchers utilized a demographic profile sheet to identify the characteristics of each participant. This sheet was divided into two sections: the first section contained the participants' personal information, while the second section contained their responses to questions related to their self-concept, specifically the Self-Objectification Beliefs and Behaviors Scale (SOBBS).

The degree to which pageant contenders engage in self-objectification was determined using the Self-Objectification Beliefs and Behaviors Scale (SOBBS) of Lindner and Tantleff-Dunn, which has an internal consistency of 0.91. The internal consistency of factor 1 (observer's perspective) was $\alpha = .89$. The alpha coefficient for factor 2 (body as self) was $\alpha = .88$. Further studies confirmed the scale's reliability and validity through various measures with internal consistency reliability ranging from $\alpha = .87$ to $\alpha = .93$ (Casalheira

et al, 2023).

There are 14 statements in the instrument (i.e., I am looking at myself from the outside). Each of the 14 items was assessed by participants on a 5-point Likert scale that went from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The score of each participant was obtained by computing the average score for each factor that includes the Observer's Perspective (i.e., 2,4,6,7,8,12,14) and the Body as Self (i.e., 1,3,5,9,10,11,13). Higher scores for each subscale indicate stronger self-objectification thoughts and behaviors (Lindner & Tantleff- Dunn, 2017).

Procedure

The researchers employed a non-probability sampling method, specifically the purposive sampling technique, to identify that female pageant participants are suitable for the study. Publication materials were disseminated in various Facebook groups within Bataan to recruit interested individuals. Female pageant contenders needed a higher average score on each Self- Objectification Beliefs and Behaviors Scale (SOBBS) subscale to measure self-objectification before providing informed consent and assent. To obtain this, researchers calculated each factor's mean scores by averaging items related to the observer's perspective (i.e., 2, 4, 6, 7, 8, 12, 14) and the body as self (i.e., 1, 3, 5, 9, 10, 11, 13) (Lindner & Tantleff- Dunn, 2017). Researchers ensured an equal chance of selection for all potential participants. The allocation of participants to the control and experimental groups was determined using a roulette wheel technique. Once participants were gathered, group chats were established for both the experimental and control groups.

A total of 15 participants completed the study, with 7 participants in the experimental group and 8 participants in the control group (Lakens, 2022). After scheduling the yoga session based on participants' availability, the researchers conducted four (4) consecutive days of Kundalini yoga sessions lasting one hour each for the experimental group. The control group received a one-time, 45 minutes mindfulness webinar. Both groups underwent pre-test and post-test assessments before and after their respective sessions. A professional yoga instructor led the yoga with the assistance of the researchers for the experimental group. Meanwhile, the control group participated in the online webinar that tackles the importance of mindfulness, led by a professional mental health advocate speaker.

Data Analysis

The researchers utilized the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) V.25 to analyze the data (Abu- Bader, 2021). Likewise, the level of significance is set at 0.05. Additionally, researchers calculated the average score for demographics and levels of self-objectification using the mean. The standard deviations determined the association between the scores, whether scattered or intact. Furthermore, the researchers employed a Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test to distinguish the mean scores between the pageant contenders' pre-tests and post-tests, and the Mann-Whitney U test established the comparison of the posttest means of the experimental and control groups (Gerald & Patson, 2021).

Ethical Considerations

Ensuring ethical standards in data collection was paramount to upholding scientific integrity, respecting human rights, and safeguarding the dignity of research participants (Jacob et al., 2022). Adhering to the 2022 Code of Ethics for Philippine Psychologists and Psychometricians, the researchers obtained informed consent from the participants and strictly adhered to ethical principles, encompassing human dignity and confidentiality. Compliance with RA 10173 also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, ensured the exclusive use of collected information for the study, maintaining participant confidentiality. The researchers conducted the study with integrity, professionalism, and a commitment to participant well-being, adhering to ethical guidelines and data privacy regulations.

Results and Discussion

Fifteen study participants completed the Self- Objectification Beliefs and Behaviors Scale (SOBBS). Among them, seven (7) were randomly allocated to the experimental group, and eight (8) were assigned to the control group. The participants had Mage = 19.87 years old (SD = 1.68) and MBMI= 20.24 (SD = 4.31). In the control group (n=8), there was a slight decrease in self-objectification. Scores transitioning from the observer's perspective decreased from $x = 3.31$ to $x = 3.00$ ($p=0.463$), and scores transitioning from the body as self decreased from $x = 2.42$ to $x = 1.27$ ($p=0.089$). A one-time mindfulness webinar may have contributed to the slight decrease in the post-test mean score of the control group.

Table 1. Mean Scores Before and After the Kundalini Yoga

Measure	Before Kundalini Yoga	After Kundalini Yoga	Difference		Effect Size
	Mean	Mean	Mean	p	
Observer's Perspective	4.04	1.55	2.49	0.018	0.89
Body as Self	3.28	1.27	2.01	0.018	0.89

Participants in the experimental group ($n = 7$), in consideration of the observer's perspective, obtained a mean of 4.04 before taking the intervention. After completing the program, the mean score significantly decreased to 1.55 ($p = 0.018$, $r = 0.89$), indicating a substantial and statistically significant difference. Additionally, the mean score for the body as self also decreased significantly from 3.28 to 1.27 ($p = 0.018$, $r = 0.89$). The domain of the observer's perspective had a more significant difference in mean score compared to the body as self. This shift in mean scores profoundly impacts the self-objectification of pageant contenders (Carey et al., 2023)

To see whether there have been any notable differences in self-objectification between the two groups, the researcher used the Mann-Whitney U test to compare the post-mean score of pageants contenders who self-objectify after the two treatments. The data revealed that the Mann-Whitney U value was 12.00, and the z-score was -1.90. Given the significance value is 0.059, it indicates that it is not significant (Cooksey, 2020).

The aim of this study is to examine the impact of Kundalini Yoga on the self-objectification of female pageant contenders (Alleva et al., 2020; Martinez et al., 2022; Rohmatin & Habsari, 2020). In line with this, the researchers investigated whether Kundalini yoga can serve as an intervention in helping women lessen their self-objectification and its adverse effects which correlates to it (Fox et al., 2021). Following the results of the study, Kundalini Yoga has significantly lowered self-objectification of pageant contenders, having a greater difference in the mean score of the observer's perspective domain. This suggests that yoga programs can reduce the self-objectification of participants (Alleva et al., 2020). Meanwhile, participants in the control group did not experience any significant changes in terms of their self-objectification. Additionally, the data suggest that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the control and experimental groups.

Remarkably, Kundalini Yoga indicates a significance with large effect size in terms of reducing the participants' self-objectification. The yoga program led to lower post-test scores for pageant contenders after the sessions. This contributes to the findings of the experiments that yoga as an intervention can lower their self-objectification and help to have a positive body image (Alleva et al., 2020). In relation to the participants' questionnaire scores, the result supports the findings of preceding studies, which propose that the implementation of yoga aided by a professional yoga instructor can help participants value themselves more internally rather than by focusing on their physical appearance (Alleva et al., 2020). During interviews conducted after the program, participants also expressed that the yoga instructor helped them feel more appreciative and aware of themselves.

According to Rohmatin & Habsari (2020), women who participate in beauty pageants are often exposed to the audience, which can lead them to view themselves as objects that require constant surveillance. The study also found that pageant contenders strive to attain a certain status to appear pleasing from other people's perspectives, which leads them to control their behavior based on how they want others to perceive them. With the study's result, the observer's perspective factor significantly dominates in the score, which suggests that Kundalini Yoga may help improve the self-esteem and self-efficacy of participants (Martinez et al., 2022; Kahkonen & Da Silva, 2023). Considering the significant effect size observed in the mean scores of pageant contenders, this suggests that the intervention could reduce the pressure for them to conform to beauty pageant standards or others' perceptions. Essentially, Kundalini Yoga may help individuals prioritize their own self-value over external judgments.

Previous studies suggest that people who struggle to define their sense of self may seek external sources to help them clarify their identity. Body as self, which values an individual's physical appearance over other features and attributes, is one of the core factors of objectification theory. This approach evaluates the body as if it could reflect the self. Researchers found that pageant contenders seek an ideal body to represent themselves. The body as self was a significant factor in the study results, indicating that engaging in Kundalini Yoga could improve one's sense of peace, self-development, and overall well-being (Kahkonen & Da Silva, 2023). Furthermore, this supports the empirical findings of other literature, which suggest that yoga helps cultivate embodying practices such as mindful self-care (Cox & Tylka, 2020). The high effect size, as self-demonstrated by the result in the domain of the body as self, amplifies the positive impact associated with kundalini yoga, which includes boosting self-perception, promoting self-compassion, and fostering a greater appreciation of oneself (Alleva et al., 2020; Dorien & Kulshrestha, 2024).

In addition, this is the first study to test these relationships based on experimental data, and the current findings are of great importance to the literature. With this, it can serve as a groundwork for future researchers and practitioners to navigate the other possible impacts of the Kundalini Yoga and similar ones to the facets of self-objectification.

To ensure the advancement of knowledge in the field, these limitations can proactively work towards addressing them in future investigations. The study requires assistance in identifying subtle effects of the intervention due to limited participants. It is vital to prioritize larger, diverse samples for more accurate and impactful results (Indrayan & Mishra, 2021). While the study primarily focuses on a particular age group, it is necessary to broaden the scope of the age range to gain more comprehensive insights into how age influences intervention effectiveness on self-objectification (Alleva et al., 2020). In addition, women's body image can differ in influence depending on the specific yoga styles and instructors they encounter (Cox & Tylka, 2020; Piran & Neumark-Sztainer, 2020). Some may emphasize body acceptance and self-compassion in their teaching, while others may focus more on physical fitness. Therefore, while investigating the effects of yoga interventions on women's self-objectification, it is crucial to consider the specific type of yoga practiced and the instructor's approach. The study venue's characteristics, including atmosphere and amenities, affect participant experiences with the intervention. Factors like noise and lighting quality influence involvement and satisfaction. Additionally, timing, encompassing various aspects like time of day and duration, is crucial for analyzing the intervention's impact

(Alleva et al., 2020).

Conclusions

This study constitutes an important progress in the investigation of Kundalini yoga's impact on self-objectification among female pageant contenders. Consistent with our hypotheses, the women who participated in the yoga group experienced enhancements and achieved diminished self-objectification, as evidenced by the substantial effect size on both the observer's perspective and the body as self. This study aligns with objectification theory observed in pageant participants and informs research on yoga's potential to improve self-esteem and body image. The findings underscore the role of Kundalini yoga in mitigating self-objectification among female pageant participants, fostering an enhanced sense of self-worth.

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